

EXPLOITATION CHARACTERISTICS OF THE RETROFITTED THYRISTOR RECTIFIERS IN AN UNINTERRUPTIBLE POWER SUPPLY SYSTEM OF A THERMAL POWER PLANT

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Abstract: Thyristor rectifiers are still the most numerous power supply devices in the internal consumption systems of the power plants and transformer substations of the Electric Power Industry of Serbia. The most of the mentioned devices were commissioned during the seventies and eighties of the last century, having analogue electronic control circuits. Many of the thyristor rectifiers were, in the meantime, retrofitted, with the basic intervention being the replacement of the old analogue electronic control units with a digital one, based on microprocessors. In this way were, with modest investments and actions, procured devices with the novel technical characteristics, yet retaining the robustness and simplicity of the old rectifiers. Nevertheless, following the multi-year exploitation of the retrofitted rectifiers, a question arises regarding the possible duration of their further use, as well as the potential for the further reconstruction of the existing thyristor AC/DC converters with analogue electronic control circuits.

In the paper was described the experience obtained during the thirteen-year exploitation of fourteen retrofitted thyristor rectifiers, operating in the thermal power plant “Nikola Tesla B”. The perceived circuit faults were described, and their causes were analysed. Opportunities for a further retrofit of the old thyristor rectifiers were evaluated, and the procedures for their implementation were proposed.

Key words: *thyristor rectifier, digital control unit, reliability*

ЕКСПЛОАТАЦИОНЕ КАРАКТЕРИСТИКЕ РЕКОНСТРУИСАНИХ ТИРИСТОРСКИХ ИСПРАВЉАЧА У СИСТЕМУ БЕСПРЕКИДНОГ НАПАЈАЊА ТЕРМОЕЛЕКТРАНЕ

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Кратак садржај: Тиристорски исправљачи су и даље најзаступљенији уређаји за напајање у системима сопствене потрошње електрана и трансформаторских станица Електропривреде Србије. Већина поменутих уређаја је уграђена током седамдесетих и осамдесетих година прошлог века, са аналогним управљачким електронским склоповима. Многи тиристорски исправљачи су у међувремену реконструисани, а основна интервенција се огледала у замени старих аналогних управљачких склопова са дигиталним, заснованим на микропроцесорским. На овај начин су, уз мале инвестиције и захвате, добијени уређаји са новим техничким карактеристикама, уз задржавање робусности и једноставности старих исправљача. Међутим, након вишегодишње експлоатације реконструисаних исправљача, поставља се питање временског ограничења њиховог даљег коришћења, као и могућности

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реконструкције постојећих тиристорских исправљача са старим аналогним електронским управљачким склоповима.

У раду је описано искуство стечено током тринаестогодишње експлоатације укупно четрнаест реконструисаних тиристорских исправљача, уграђених у термоелектрани “Никола Тесла Б”. Наведени су уочени откази склопова и анализирани су њихови узроци. Процењене су могућности за даљу реконструкцију старих тиристорских исправљача, а предложени су и поступци за примену предложених решења.

Кључне речи: *тиристорски исправљач, дигитална управљачка електроника, поузданост*

1. INTRODUCTION

Beside the implementation of the new high-frequency power electronic systems, characterized by the high power quality and power-efficiency, exploitation of the old thyristor converters is still justified [1-3]. Thyristor rectifiers have a high power efficiency [3], often surpassing their more modern, high-frequency counterparts with the same level of electrical isolation. Nevertheless, high-frequency AC/DC converters have the great advantages in the area of power quality. Operation of high-frequency devices is characterized by the high power factor ($\cos\phi > 0.95$) [3] and low total current harmonic distortion ($THDi < 5\%$). Yet, in the existing power plants and transformer substations, where the issues of power quality are not priority, retention of the thyristor devices is a rational option. This is particularly true in the direct current uninterruptible power supply (UPS) systems, operating with the fully loaded battery for a most of the lifetime. Thus, such rectifiers would, for most of its exploitation life, operate with 20-30 % of the nominal load [2]. Also, taking into account their nominal power, being in the range of 5 – 10 kVA in most of the transformer substations, a conclusion can be drawn that AC/DC converters in UPS systems would seldom be the generators of the unsustainable level of high-order harmonics.

Thyristor rectifiers are very robust devices, with a mature technology and a simple power circuit [3]. They are usually well known to the local service personnel, with an abundance of spare parts and available remote technical support. It is not unusual for thyristor rectifiers to operate, almost constantly, for a thirty or more years. So, old devices in the power industry objects should be considered as candidates for a further operation even after expiry of the nominal service life, usually being 20-25 years [1]. Nevertheless, these devices would hardly reach such long service life without proper maintenance, let alone to operate reliably all this time. Therefore, it is necessary to specify what would be the most robust parts, suitable for preservation, and what circuits should be change during the retrofit procedure.

2. CHARACTERISTICS OF THE RETROFITTED RECTIFIERS AND DIGITAL CONTROL UNITS “DRI 05”

In the thermal power plant “Nikola Tesla B”, near town of Obrenovac, Serbia, in total fourteen rectifiers of “TPA” series were embedded in the UPS system. These devices were designed to charge the accompanying lead-acid batteries and supply the critical load, at the voltage levels of 24 V, 48 V and 220 V. Battery chargers have various powers, from 10 kVA up to 160 kVA. Devices are charging vented lead-acid batteries, having capacities ranging from 420 Ah up to 1200 Ah. They were manufactured in 1982, by “Energoinvest” company, and incessantly supplied the direct current to the critical load from the power plant commissioning, in 1983. From November 2005 to August 2009, rectifiers were thoroughly reconstructed. Battery chargers were retrofitted with the new digital control unit of “DRI 05” type [4]. Beside the electronic control circuit, also were replaced all light signalization, low-cross-section cables, and relays (contactors and switches were replaced little

later). The power circuit and mechanical construction were completely retained: transformer, inductor, thyristor bridge, high-current fuses, shunts, cabinet, power cables, bus bars, instruments.

Retrofitted rectifier DRI 24-250 (nominal output parameters: 24 V, 250 A) was presented in Fig. 1. It may be clearly seen that the most of the power circuit and mechanical parts were retained, while the control and signalling equipment was replaced. The main new part, “DRI 05” digital control unit, was embedded in an aluminium box and mounted in the steel frame, situated in the middle of the rectifier. From the perspective of the user, rectifier was significantly simplified, since many of the original low-voltage equipment and relays were now removed.

Fig. 1. a) Internal appearance of the retrofitted rectifier DRI 24-250 in the thermal power plant “Nikola Tesla B”; b) internal appearance of the digital control unit “DRI 05”.

The basic construction of rectifiers was based on a thyristor half-bridge, made in 1982 by “AEG”. These power converters are standard line-frequency AC/DC converters, operating with the inherent frequency of 150 Hz. Rectifier has only inductive output filter, since the storage battery performs role of the capacitive filter. Rectifier was not designed to operate without a battery. Line voltage was introduced to the power circuit using the input contactor.

Digital control unit for thyristor rectifiers, the “DRI 05” type, was initially developed in Electrical engineering Institute “Nikola Tesla”, in 2005, primarily for the retrofit of the old rectifiers in the thermal power plant “Nikola Tesla B” [2, 4]. These digital control units were at the same time embedded in several new thyristor rectifiers, made for other users in Serbia. The control unit has a modular construction, with only three boards (power supply, analogue motherboard and microprocessor card) in the aluminium box. The power board was supplied from two sides at the same time: from the battery, as well as from the mains grid. All the analogue circuits (line synchronisation signal, measurement, inputs and output signals, thyristor drivers), as well as electrically isolated RS-485 serial communication circuit [5, 6], were integrated on a single motherboard, called “DIGISP 05”. There was maximum attempt to perform electric isolation of both input and output signals from the control unit. All the thyristor driver pulses were transferred via pulse transformers. Input signals were transferred via optocouplers, with the special local power

supply. Output signals (except for LED signalization) were transferred via PCB relays. All three phases of the mains supply were adjusted by the print-transformers.

Digital control was based on a printed circuit board (PCB) called “uP3”, with microprocessor “Intel” 80C196KB16 [2, 4, 7]. All the control, protection and communication sequences were unified on the same card. Serial communication was based on the proprietary protocol INT-CPD-05, with a baud rate of 1200 bit/s [6]. One power relay may be used as a remote signalization of the rectifier failure or turn-off. The input contactor auxiliary contact of may be used as another remote signalization.

There are three basic modes of the battery charging: float charge (2.23 V per battery cell), boost charge (2.42 V/cell) and equalizing charge (2.65 V/cell) [4, 8]. Beside three manual regimes, there is also an automatic mode of operation, enabling the battery charging according to IUU characteristic. All of the mentioned modes of operation have appropriate current limits, when the controller switches from the voltage regulation to the current regulation, and vice versa, either in manual modes or automatic operation [4, 7, 8].

Rectifier has the following protection functions, with local signalization: mains failure, high battery voltage, battery failure, current overload, low battery voltage, as well as a thyristor bridge failure [4]. If some of the first four protection functions are activated, the rectifier is automatically turned off, and then commence an automatic triple restart sequence, with an intermediate 30 second period for the following automatic turn on. If there are three unsuccessful automatic attempts to recover AC/DC converter from failure, then automatic restart sequences terminate and the failure signalization remains until the user intervention.

In general, the design of the “DRI 05” control unit, as well as the retrofitted battery charger, was oriented toward the simplicity, robustness, high reliability and longevity of the rectifier. More details about thyristor rectifiers and accompanying DRI series control units may be found in literature [2], [4-8].

3. EXPLOITATION PERIOD AFTER RECONSTRUCTION

Following the reconstruction of the first AC/DC converter, users from the Electric Power Industry of Serbia performed observance and the basic maintenance of retrofitted rectifiers, while the manufacturer of “DRI 05” units have done regular annual maintenance, as well as additional improvements of control circuits and entire rectifiers. All the maintenance actions were mutually coordinated between users and manufacturer. Thus, most of the details from the exploitation history, lasting from nine up to thirteen years, are now well known to the author.

Throughout its service life, retrofitted rectifiers were subjected to the constant improvement. This was primarily related to the control software. Many improvements, made by the manufacturer of “DRI 05” type devices, were quickly implemented in the control software of the microprocessor card. Initially, basic controller functions remained the same, yet the more efficient control algorithms were implemented.

Permanent exploitation in the harsh industrial conditions pointed to the great significance of suppression of the electromagnetic interference, both on the mains supply side and DC side. These interventions significantly improved the rectifier robustness, making them less prone to the resets caused by the commutation overvoltages in the facility.

Nevertheless, after the capital reconstruction of one power block of a thermal power plant, users asked to connect all the thyristor rectifiers with the new SCADA system, using standard “Modbus RTU” protocol [6]. While this was not possible with the initial configuration of “DRI 05” control unit, significant improvements were made either on software and hardware, yet retaining the original microprocessor. The new telecommunication network was laid between the rectifiers. The devices were connected to the protocol converter INT-485-MBRTU [6], based on the programmable logic controller “Omron” CJ1M. This protocol converter enabled connection of “DRI 05” units, operating with a proprietary protocol INT-CPD-05 [6], with the new SCADA system, using the “Modbus RTU” communication protocol.

Implementation of an on-line serial communication additionally burdened the only microprocessor, making it more prone to faults. Thus, the logic of the accompanying watchdog-timers were changed, in order to prevent permanent controller failure, whatever happened to the serial communication lines. Also, logic for the activation of the input contactor was changed, in order to prevent the unwanted turn off of the input contactor.

It should be repeated that new digital controllers were commissioned successively, in the period of nearly four years. Also, battery chargers are such devices that operate almost uninterruptedly year-around, with the exception of a ten-hour period during the battery discharge, performed once a year. Taking into account all the specified facts, it could be estimated that fourteen retrofitted rectifiers, from November 23rd, 2005, up to June 30th, 2018, accumulated approximately 1,313,000 working hours in the thermal power plant “Nikola Tesla B”.

There were identified seven failures of the “DRI 05” digital control units. Details on these events were presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Chronology of faults observed on the retrofitted rectifiers in the thermal power plant “Nikola Tesla B”

Num-ber of fail-ure	Date	Description of the battery charger failure	Cause	Observation of failure	Conse-quence	Comment
1.	April 2008	Failure of input contactor	Contactors coil failure	During the regular operation	Battery charger turn-off	Failure happened with old contactor, prior to their complete replacement with new devices
2.	June 2008	Failure of overvoltage protection	Fuse blow in one mains supply phase, followed by the increase of referent voltage, done by unauthorized personnel	During the regular operation	Continued battery charger operation with signalization of unsymmetrical thyristor bridge operation	Maintenance personnel quickly transferred DC load on the spare battery charger. Faulty rectifier was returned in service after the intervention of the manufacturer of the control circuit unit. Overvoltage protection was later improved by manufacturer.
3.	January 2011	Failure of signalling relays and power relay in digital unit “DRI 05”, as well as in the battery charger cabinet	Heavy incident in the adjacent room	During the regular operation	Continued battery charger operation without failure signalling	Maintenance personnel quickly installed spare card and power relay. Soon after this intervention rectifier continued its operation. Manufacturer later repaired defective printed circuit board.

4.	June 2011	Failure of integrated circuit (parallel interface, 82C55) on the micro-processor card “uP3”	Unknown	Perceived during the planned periodical maintenance	Did not affect the battery charger proper operation	Replaced during the planned periodical service
5.	December 2015	Micro-processor card failure	Software failure occurred soon after installation of the local communication network	During the test operation	Battery charger turn-off	Watchdog timer failed to react – battery charger went back into operation after manual microprocessor reset by the maintenance personnel.
6.	April 2016	Failure of a torus transformer, designed for a power supply of the control unit “DRI 05” with alternate current	Unknown	Perceived during the planned periodical maintenance	Did not affect the battery charger proper operation	Replaced during the planned periodical maintenance.
7.	April 2016	Micro-processor card failure	Bad solder connections on a printed circuit board (PCB)	Perceived during the planned periodical maintenance	Did not affect the battery charger proper operation	Fixed during the planned periodical maintenance.

Thus, according to the presented data on these seven events, the total mean time between failure was nearly $MTBF(t) = 187,571$ hours. If the heavy incident was excluded from the calculation (in that situation, it was surprising that battery charger even continued to operate), then we may calculate empirical mean time between failure, $MTBF(e) = 218,833$ hours. If the data on faults perceived during the regular maintenance were omitted, then we may get mean time between failures that affected the battery charger operation: $MTBF(a) = 328,250$ hours. Finally, if we observe only “hard failures”, when the battery charger turned off and left batteries without power supply, then we get: $MTBF(h) = 437,667$ hours. Since the batteries were connected to the output of battery chargers, and simultaneously with DC load, none of these three hard failures caused the outage of the entire block of the power plant.

4. DISCUSSION

As may be seen from Table 1, there were not many faults observed during the battery chargers long lasting operation. It is very important that neither of the observed failures caused the thermal power plant outage, since a new start of such a big power object is always costly and time-consuming. Nevertheless, the primary reason for this is a principle of operation of DC UPS systems, since, in such cases, storage batteries are the foundation of the security and power supply systems. Thus, it is

another illustration of the great importance of the storage battery maintenance and their timely replacement.

Another important conclusion is the importance of the periodical maintenance. In the thermal power plant “Nikola Tesla B”, there is a standard practice that every year, during the planned maintenance of the entire facility, manufacturers perform thorough inspection of power converters in UPS systems. Thus, in the case of battery chargers, three of seven reported failures (43 %) were eliminated before they could affect the rectifier operation. Also, massive stock of spare parts also played its role, since both in the cases of regular operation or the planned maintenance, all the necessary parts were available in the power plant, reducing the time-to-repair to a minimum.

Data from Table 1 point to a wide spectrum of the potential failures, from electromechanical devices up to the software issues. Thus, in all the cases, it is very important to have the well-trained maintenance personnel. Also, it is a duty of manufacturer to devise and clearly describe simple repair procedures, in order to enable maintenance personnel to react correctly and promptly on a very broad spectrum of potential problems in exploitation of power converters. Another important issue is to deliver to the user adjusted electronic circuit boards whenever it is possible. In the case when all potentiometers on PCBs are properly adjusted, and when up-to-date software is uploaded in microprocessor cards, maintenance personnel in the power object may quickly replace the defective card, without the need for urgent intervention from the manufacturer. Taking into account very high costs of the long-lasting outage of big industrial facilities, we recommend to the users to insist on delivery of adjusted spare electronic cards as soon as the commissioning of power converters was performed.

Preventive maintenance also demonstrated their advantages. Gained experience justifies timely replacement of electromechanical components (primarily contactors and switches) as soon as their operational life comes to an end. Failure of the input power contactor certainly leads to the battery charger turn-off. Defective switch may also have hard consequences. In power objects, switches may be often affected by a harsh industrial conditions, particularly dust, smoke and high temperature. Thus, as soon as initial problems had been reported with contactors and switches, all these devices from initial installation were replaced during the next planned periodical maintenance.

Introduction of the serial communication may significantly affect the power converter reliability. If there are separate processors (or separate cores in the same microcontroller package), with the existence of independent units completely dedicated to the serial communication, this, most often, would not be an issue that could affect the power converter operation. Nevertheless, if the same microprocessor performs both control and communication tasks, connection of digital control units should be carefully considered. In such a case, it would be wise to use two watchdog timers (a software and a hardware one), in order to practically eliminate the possibility of a long-lasting outage of a UPS system (by the way, many modern microcontroller already offer such an option, integrated in the same case). If battery charger was not designed to operate without storage battery, short-term turn-off due to watchdog-timer reaction is usually harmless. Nevertheless, if battery charger was designed to operate both with and without a connected storage battery, users should be very careful with connection of these devices to a communication network. In such cases, if there is not a separate microprocessor unit, dedicated only to a serial communication, we recommend to potential users to perform remote supervision and control by using relay contacts or transducers, rather than to add communication tasks to control-oriented microcontrollers.

Another important conclusion that may be drawn is that there was not failures of thyristor bridges! In the last 13 years, we have not noticed any case of failure of the power semiconductor switches (thyristors and diodes) or accompanying rapid fuses. Thus, it is one of the most important recommendation to users prior to making the decision for battery chargers retrofit. If old thyristor rectifiers already contain reliable thyristors, compatible with drivers of the potential digital control unit, it is justified to consider the AC/DC converter reconstruction. If thyristors are prone to failures, or are of some old types, not compatible with modern drivers, battery charger retrofit should be considered only in the case when replacement of entire thyristor bridges was also

considered.

The similar principle is valid also for inductive elements – isolation transformers and inductors. The bad condition of these dry-type elements may be the greatest obstacle for the successful retrofit of battery chargers. Bad transformer isolation usually leads to heavy failures, with a heavy damage of copper windings. Such repairs are time-consuming and very expensive, so they are rarely justified. On the other hand, the purchase of a new, low-frequency transformer, is also very expensive and time-consuming procedure. Also, due to the spatial restrictions, new transformer, not manufactured by the customer-made project, often could not have been embedded in an old cabinet! So, in most cases, bad state of the inductive elements should be the greatest obstacle for the successful retrofit of the old thyristor rectifiers.

One of the main conclusions, obtained in previous years, is that reconstruction of the thyristor rectifier should enable further modernization potential. This is particularly true in the case of the electronic control circuit. The main reason is the necessity for a future harmonization with the accompanying equipment, such as SCADA systems or telecommunication networks. Thus, the main modernization potential should not be related to a power circuit, but rather electronic control unit.

5. CONCLUSION

More than decade long experience from exploitation of fourteen retrofitted thyristor rectifiers was presented in the paper. AC/DC converters, with original analogue electronic control units, were thoroughly reconstructed after 23 to 27 years of exploitation. After more than a decade of almost uninterrupted operation, thyristor rectifiers demonstrated reliable and secure operation. The devices were permanently improved during the previous years, further increasing their telecommunication capabilities, as well as immunity to electromagnetic interference. Now 36 years old battery chargers still operate in a UPS system of a thermal power plant, being far away from the end of their service life.

From the end of 2005 up to the 2018, retrofitted rectifiers accumulated approximately 1,313,000 working hours. During this period, seven failures were identified, with one of them being the consequence of the emergency situations in the facility, while the remaining six occurred during the regular operation. Three of the mentioned failures originating from the regular operation conditions were detected and fixed during the regular yearly service. Thus, empirically detected mean time between failures, excluding the incidents that caused damage of battery chargers, was equal to the $MTBF(e) = 218,833$ hours. If only “hard failures” were observed, when the battery charger turned off and left batteries without power supply during regular operation, then is $MTBF(h) = 437,667$ hours. None of the registered failures caused the interruption of the power plant operation.

The mentioned data justified performed reconstruction of the old thyristor rectifiers. Removing the most sensitive parts of battery chargers, that are old electronic and mechanical components, and build in of the modern digital control units, enabled the reliable device operation for a next decade. Even more, present situation points to the possible operation even at least for a decade more. Thus, operation life of thyristor rectifiers, embedded in power plants and transformer substations, may be extended from the nominal 20-25 years, up to 40-45 years.

In order to enable such a long operation period, it is necessary to build an up-to-date electronic control unit, having pretty advanced technical characteristics in a time of reconstruction. If it is not possible, then a possibility should be left for significant future improvements of a new controller. This is necessary in order to enable connection of a digital control unit with an accompanying telecommunication and computer equipment, enabling mutual compatibility in a period of the following one or two decades. Another, maybe even more important condition, is to train the maintenance personnel, being in charge with the equipment. Also, sufficient amount of the spare parts must be immediately acquired for a planned period of the extended exploitation. Complying with all the presented recommendations is a certain way to substantially extend the

service life of the old battery chargers.

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